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AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL: A CRITICAL TEACHER'S LOOK AT INCLUSIVE EDUCATIONAL PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

The article addresses the discussion within and outside the educational setting, precisely because it does not exclusively involve education professionals, but families are considered highly relevant to the student's educational progress. Autism should not be treated as a pathology. It is possible to integrate these students into the regular classroom. The educator is the main agent of transformation, even in the absence of support and working conditions, where they reinvent themselves and adapt to help these learners in the most dignified and respectful way possible. This research included the participation of elementary school teachers from the municipal public school system in the municipality of Vargem Alta, Espírito Santo, specifically children with ASD enrolled in regular education classrooms at Pedro Milaneze Altoé High School. The main study analyzed teachers' perspectives on the teaching and learning offered to elementary school students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). There is a great interest from management and teachers in understanding students with ASD, thus enabling new forms of learning for the student, providing quality of life and quality of teaching-learning offered, strengthening autonomy and the continuous insertion of the inclusion process.

Keywords: Autism. Inclusion. Integration. Inclusive practice.

INTRODUCTION

Inclusion focuses on the student and must reach everyone, with the goal of developing learning. It is the teacher's responsibility to focus on their students, acting as a facilitator of this inclusion, guiding, observing, and listening attentively to each of their learners. Educators must have the ability to understand and critically analyze the reality they experience, all social aspects, and even human relationships (LUCK, 2018).

Disability should not be viewed, in isolation, as an obstacle or impediment that prevents the full development of a person's potential. Restrictions arise from exclusionary structures and the objective conditions of the various fields of action within the social context. Each individual thinks and acts differently, and the same is true for students from inclusion programs. Therefore, educators must consider their students and identify their true needs, desires, and timeframes, adapting teaching methodology and treatment (CARVALHO, 2016).

The presence of the teacher, as a "link in the teaching-learning process," fosters citizenship awareness. Therefore, inclusion will only be successful with their full professional engagement, as they must accept and understand the inclusion process for it to truly materialize.

Nogueira (2020) states that for this practice, an open attitude toward everything and everyone is necessary, open to their knowledge and their lack of knowledge. This is precisely the big problem: "being open to your lack of knowledge." Without an attitude of humility and acknowledgment of their lack of knowledge before their peers, teachers are unwilling to engage in exchanges with other specialists.

In this author's analysis, it was noted that in an attempt to offer qualified education to integrated students, teachers need to acquire new skills to work with all students from different social

backgrounds. Therefore, a process of professional transformation is inevitable, where teachers have the opportunity to develop their skills in an atmosphere of camaraderie, collaboration, and mutual support, continually improving their knowledge.

The education of people with disabilities is a process that began on the world stage in the 17th century. This educational work encountered numerous obstacles, based on religious, mystical, and social issues, which conceived of people with disabilities as possessing a kind of karma, or as sinners, or as a burden to society and the job market (JANNUZZI, 2014).

School inclusion isn't limited to integrating students with autism into the educational environment, much less into regular teaching and learning classes. The challenge of inclusion encompasses the entire school institution in a movement toward growth and learning, beyond the existing crack in the suppressive logic that views all individuals equally, not in the sense of equality, but as generators of a single way of thinking, with the same learning time and actions. An inclusive educational institution can deal with diversity and learn from it, striving to teach and share experiences with its students in the best possible way.

According to Paulo Freire (1981), just as no one educates anyone, no one educates themselves alone. For the author, people, as individuals, educate each other, spread throughout the world. In other words, inclusion occurs when the opportunity is provided to both the student and the teacher, as well as to all those involved in the educational process, with active participation in the teaching-learning process.

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION AND ITS PARTICULARITIES

Inclusive education is vitally necessary, taking into account the individual differences of each person. This includes and welcomes people with disabilities, ensuring that everyone has the opportunity to receive education and feels part of

the pursuit of knowledge. This idea needs to be disseminated throughout the school community so that inclusion occurs not only within the classroom but also across the entire community, especially when it comes to autistic students who have socialization difficulties. In turn, it is equally important to teach that inclusive education means ensuring equal educational opportunities for all students, without exception, regardless of their sociocultural background and psychobiological development (FLEIGER, 2020).

Inclusion has been strengthened through national and international movements seeking to develop inclusive education policies. Its culmination was the World Conference on Special Education in Salamanca, Spain, in 1994, with the participation of 88 countries and 25 international organizations (Brazil, 1994). The event, entitled "The Salamanca Manifesto", brings important perspectives that should serve as reflections and changes for the current reality, which is so hostile.

SCHOOL INCLUSION OF AUTISTIC CHILDREN IN SCHOOLS

The inclusion of an autistic child in a regular educational institution raises significant concerns, whether on the part of the family or even the school itself. When this situation occurs, families and education professionals face questions about the inclusion of these children, as the school must undergo structural, methodological, and curricular adjustments (BRANDE AND ZANFELICE 2012).

However, according to Scardua (2008), this task is not easy. For school inclusion to occur, there must be commitment from everyone involved: students, teachers, parents, community, principal—in other words, everyone who participates directly or indirectly in the individual's school life.

According to Libâneo (2014), the curriculum represents the realization and promotion of the intentions expressed in the pedagogical project. It should include processes such as: a set of disciplines, intended learning outcomes,

experiences to be provided to students, guiding principles of practice, selection, and cultural organization. To hold the attention of the autistic student during classes, the teacher must use educational methodologies that aim to ensure that the student is truly included and that the teaching-learning process is effective. Therefore, many studies are carried out on differentiated methods.

METHODOLOGY

A theoretical bibliographical research with an analytical focus was also conducted, using theoretical frameworks from authors who discuss this topic. Thus, the focus was on the Pedro Milaneze Altoé EMEB, located in the São José district at Rua Caetano Vanini, S/N, Zip Code 29295-000, in the city of Vargem Alta, Espírito Santo. The target population is teachers who teach elementary school students from 1st to 9th grade and who have students with ASD enrolled in regular education at the school.

To carry out and develop this scientific research study, the research was based on a qualitative approach, bibliographical research, and field research, including the administration of a questionnaire to teachers.

The population of participants in this research was determined using criteria that ensure the experience to be described and the analysis of social practices for inclusive education. Therefore, the universe is the Pedro Milaneze Altoé School, whose sample consisted of six teachers who work in elementary school (1st to 9th grade) and who have students with autism in their classrooms.

The state of Espírito Santo is located in the Southeast region of the country and has a territorial area of 46,095.583 km², encompassing 78 municipalities, with a total state population of 3,833,486. The state capital is Vitória, which has a population of 322,869; according to information released in the 2022 census, people living in the state are called Capixabas (GOVERNMENT OF THE STATE OF ESPÍRITO SANTO, 2023).

Geographical position of the study site

Source: Government of the State of Espírito Santo, 2023.

MUNICIPALITY OF VARGEM ALTA, ESPÍRITO SANTO

The municipality of Vargem Alta was created by Law No. 4,063 of May 6, 1988, and established on January 1, 1989. The municipality is located at a south latitude of 20°, 40', and 17" and a west longitude of 41°, 39', and 37". It has an area of 417 km², equivalent to 0.91% of the state's territory. The municipality borders the cities of Domingos Martins to the south; Itapemirim to the south; Rio Novo do Sul and Alfredo Chaves to the east; and Cachoeiro de Itapemirim and Castelo to the west. It is 136 kilometers from the state capital, Vitória (IBGE, 2012).

The Pedro Milaneze Altoé School is located at Rua Caetano Vanini, s/n São José de Fruteiras. In the municipality of Vargem Alta, its main function is to respect and value the life experiences of students and their families, strengthening students' human attitude and the values they learn: critical thinking, sensitivity, social challenge, creativity in the face of difficult situations, and, ultimately, educating for life.

Map of the Municipality of Vargem Alta / ES

Source: IBGE, 2022.

The socioeconomic profile is quite diverse, but most students fall within the minimum income bracket, relying on school grant programs and aid for the purchase of materials. The school has some students with disabilities, although in some aspects the school has adequate physical infrastructure to meet the needs of these students.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All results presented below were obtained after the data collection process (questionnaire), in order to be coded and analyzed. At this point, the interpretation of the data began in the form of a descriptive analytical analysis.

The question asks professionals about the encouragement of training or lectures by the Department of Education or the institution's manager, so that students with ASD can be better received.

Table - Incentive on ASD by the SME or

TEACHERS	ANSWERS
P1	Yes. "The SME occasionally provides courses to teachers who work in the resource room."
P2	Yes. "The SME is concerned and sometimes invites teachers to participate in training in the area (Resource Room)."
P3	No. "Inclusion is rarely remembered by the SME."
P4	No. "Just the school teacher who sometimes guides me, even then, because I look for her."
P5	No. "I've never been invited to any course by the SME, in fact I've been working at the school for over 6 years with students with disabilities and nothing."
P6	No.

Source: Research data, 2023.

As can be seen, the data highlight that there is still a significant lack of assistance from administrators and the SME to teachers in seeking information aimed at welcoming students with ASD in schools. Specialized training, lectures, courses, and other resources capable of expanding the knowledge base of teaching professionals enrich this contact with students with ASD, providing them with more

efficient teaching methods, with greater understanding, comprehension, and respect within school environments.

For Mantoan (2013), all levels of academic training and teacher preparation require modifications and adaptations to their curricula, enabling future professionals to learn teaching practices appropriate to differences.

The following question asked professionals about the use of strategies and/or practices in their planning, in order to encourage the participation of students with ASD in classes.

Table: Strategies in Planning

TEACHERS	ANSWERS
P1	"Yes, I try to make adaptations to the content that is being worked on with the class."
P2	"Yes, I often look for strategies that can involve the student in participating."
P3	"Yes, but I haven't been completely successful yet, often the student doesn't participate and gets stuck in their own little world."
P4	"No, sometimes."
P5	"Yes, I seek information from my colleagues and apply strategies suggested by them, which have been successful and have worked so far."
P6	"Yes, I often look through projects I read in magazines that were successful and included my students."

Source: Research data, 2023.

According to the data above, the educators in the study use inclusive strategies and practices in their planning to improve student participation in the classroom. Only one interviewee stated that they do not use these methods, claiming to only use them occasionally.

In the words of Mantoan (2013), when teaching students with ASD, educators must provide opportunities for the development of intellectual and social skills, developing a plan to include the entire class, without discrimination or exclusion of any student. The school and the welcoming teacher make a difference in the development of the student with ASD, with the teacher carrying out various activities involving games, painting, music, among others.

The next Table refers to the communication means that the professional most uses to communicate with their autistic student.

Table: Most used means of communication

PROFESSORES	RESPOSTAS
P1	"Fala e escrita"
P2	"Gestos"
P3	"Escrita e sinais"
P4	"Fala e escrita"
P5	"Fala, gestos e sinais"
P6	"Fala, escrita e gestos"

Source: Research data, 2023.

According to the data collected in the survey, speech is the most frequently used method by teachers. Writing comes next, being the most considered option by the interviewees, and finally, writing. Teachers stated that they use gestures/signs most frequently.

This adaptation is extremely necessary for the student's learning development process. The teachers emphasized that the option chosen during this survey refers to the communication method they use most. However, just as each student has their own individuality, these professionals try to communicate with each student in the way that best facilitates teaching.

From this perspective, Wing (1985) observes that students may have difficulty programming and structuring speech, and in some situations, they may only use unintelligible jargon with grammatical structure and immature phonology.

The next approach concerns the participation and cooperation of the families of students with ASD.

Table: Family participation

TEACHERS	ANSWERS
P1	"Superficial"
P2	"Don't worry at any time."
P3	"Always seek contact with the school."
P4, P5, P6	"Participatory".

Source: Research data, 2023.

As can be seen, the professionals interviewed believe that the families of students with ASD are involved. Others believe that families offer only superficial cooperation. The same data were obtained for the option in which families show no concern at all. Among those who always seek contact with the school, this was indicated by only one professional.

Parents of individuals with ASD should be the first to identify that something unusual is happening with their child. It is at this point that the search for help begins, navigating a period of uncertainty that precedes the process of developing and establishing a diagnosis (ONZI and GOMES, 2015).

Regarding the behaviors and interests of autistic students, professionals were asked about those that are most observed in these classroom interactions, as shown in the table below.

Table - Student behaviors and interests

TEACHERS	ANSWERS
P1	"Relate to classmates."
P2	"Resists participating in proposed activities and/or routine changes."
P3	"Resists physical contact and shows fear."
P4	"Maintain eye contact with teacher and classmates."
P5	"Maintain eye contact with teacher and classmates."
P6	"Inappropriately holds objects and/or rotates objects"

Source: Research data, 2023.

It was found that in relationships with peers, students who follow orders are more frequent. One teacher observed resistance among autistic students to participating in proposed activities and/or routine changes. With the same rate as the previous options, another interviewee stated that students maintain greater eye contact with the teacher and peers.

One finding reported by the teachers was that autistic students use touch extensively, picking up and turning objects, often inappropriately.

The study concludes that the profile of the teaching staff is comprised of experienced teachers who are committed to the comprehensive education of their students. This demonstrates consistency in the interviewees' responses regarding the institution's design, as all adopted an interactionist stance, focused on mediation and the development of their students' knowledge.

The work is carried out with diverse materials and activities aimed at fostering student participation and, above all, motivating them. Everyone is aware of the difficulties encountered in the school's daily routine and that working with students with ASD is a challenge. However,

it is clear that the school is committed to the development of these children and strives for quality education.

CONCLUSION

The main objective of this article was to analyze the educational practices of teachers who work with autistic students in order to ensure quality inclusive education in a municipal public school in Vargem Alta, Espírito Santo.

The school focused on students enrolled in Pedro Milaneze Altoé Elementary School (1st to 9th grade). The problem at hand was to determine the main challenges faced by teachers and the teaching strategies they used to include these students, as well as address the importance of the educational space for their development.

After analyzing the collected data, significant results were found, including the existence of a culture of inclusion and the implementation of educational practices by teachers who teach at Pedro Milaneze Altoé Elementary School, in compliance with current legislative principles. Furthermore, there is a strong interest among management and faculty in understanding students with ASD, thus enabling new ways of learning for students, improving the quality of teaching and learning offered, and also improving quality of life, strengthening autonomy, and the ongoing inclusion process.

Another point highlighted by teachers in the survey refers to the lack of encouragement from the public agency (SME) regarding training courses, information, and demonstrations about autism.

Even so, it is believed that the training and information these educators receive are insufficient to work appropriately and meaningfully with these students.

Still, for autistic students to develop their skills, an efficient school structure is necessary, with excellent professional preparation for all those involved in the teaching-learning process. The difficulty autistic students have in adapting to the outside world was exposed, and therefore, it is up to the school to consider adapting the

context. It is understood that there are not only inclusive classrooms, but also inclusive schools. Therefore, it is necessary for the institution to create a routine of situations in time and space, constituting strategies for the adaptation and development of these students.

For this to happen, the school must promote an education that respects the diversity of each student, teaching and motivating students to live with diversity and differences within the school environment, with respect and understanding so that there is no room for discrimination, thus overcoming the differences and particularities of each individual; knowing that student learning depends on the stimulation provided by the teacher and all the individuals within the institution.

Within this scenario, the need to coexist socially and learn to live within diversity is recommended. For this reason, it is necessary to develop a new concept of teaching and learning, and with this thought, the concepts of inclusion and integration are realized.

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